

Identifying trees through dichotomous keys

Muzzini V.G.^a, Brunacci L.^a, Cardettini G.^b, Pulze C.^a, Bertolotto P.^a

a – CNR - Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, SP35d, n. 9, 00010 Montelibretti (RM), Italia

b – CNR - Regional Research Campus of Rome 1 (ARRM1), SP35d, n. 9, 00010 Montelibretti (RM), Italia

Introduction

The Researchers' Night is an initiative promoted by the European Commission since 2005, involving thousands of researchers and research institutions in all European countries.

The aim is to create opportunities for researchers and citizens to meet in order to spread scientific culture and knowledge of research professions in an informal and stimulating environment.

Events include live scientific experiments and demonstrations, exhibitions and guided tours, conferences and outreach seminars, performances and concerts¹.

Italy has joined the European initiative with a multitude of projects that make it one of the European countries with the largest number of events spread over the territory.

The Research Area Rome 1 of CNR in Montelibretti (42.10576N, 12.63737E) has also joined the European initiative, proposing several initiatives within the spaces of the Area. One of the most important focuses on biodiversity. Within this research topic, we proposed an educational activity to teach citizens how to identify plants, especially trees, using dichotomous keys.

The initiative aims to introduce the fascinating world of plants by learning how to identify them with scientific methods. Learning to recognize trees is a valuable skill that allows us to appreciate the biodiversity around us, develop a sense of connection with nature and contribute to environmental protection.

CNR - Rome 1 Research Area - Montelibretti

European Researchers' Night Activities

Ten potted trees, numbered 1-10 and selected from the Montelibretti Research Area (Table 1), will be presented to participants. Guided by a series of binary or multiple-choice questions, participants will examine the visible characteristics of each tree (macroscopic traits) to identify its species through a process of elimination.

Table 1 – Selection of trees from the Research Area Roma 1 - CNR

Tree	Scientific Name	Coordinates Position
PINE	<i>Pinus halepensis</i> Mill	N 42°06.146' E 12°38.224'
SPRUCE	<i>Picea abies</i> (L.) H. Karst	N 42°06.145' E 12°38.228'
CYPRESS	<i>Cupressus arizonica</i> E. Greene	N 42°06.153' E 12°38.252'
ROBINIA	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	N 42°06.177' E 12°38.206'
WALNUT	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	N 42°06.427' E 12°38.215'
WHITE POPLAR	<i>Populus alba</i> L.	N 42°06.473' E 12°38.277'
BLACK POPLAR	<i>Populus nigra</i> L.	N 42°06.318' E 12°38.208'
OAK	<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	N 42°06.478' E 12°38.301'
LIME	<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	N 42°06.430' E 12°38.269'
BLACK MULBERRY	<i>Morus nigra</i> L.	N 42°06.472' E 12°38.291'

On the morning of the event, a branch from each tree will be placed in a numbered pot. All potted branches will be displayed on a table at the event.

Dichotomous Key

A specialized dichotomous key (Appendix 1) has been created for the event, featuring key characteristics for identifying the selected tree species. Participants will receive a copy and attempt to identify the trees on display.

An operator will guide participants through using the dichotomous key, explaining its methodology and its broader applications beyond plant recognition. Visual aids (Appendix 2) will support participants in identifying specific traits. These visual aids were created by editing photos with ImageJ software (Appendix 3) and highlighting key features with GIMP software (Appendix 4). An operator will be available to answer questions. Participants who successfully identify all ten plants will receive a copy of the dichotomous key as a memento of this initiative.

Conclusions

The proposed activity will offer the public the opportunity to learn about the scientific method used for plant identification and to demonstrate its applicability in various fields. The goal is to promote the dissemination of scientific culture in an engaging way and to create new multidisciplinary links between research and citizens.

References

1. <https://www.nottedeiricercatori.it/>

APPENDIX 1 – KEY TO TREE RECOGNITION – RESEARCH NIGHT 2024

N	Leaf description	Specie	Scientific name
01	Needle leaves	02	
	Leaves with a larger surface	05	
02	Single needles	03	
	clumps of 2 needles	PINE	<i>Pinus halepensis Mill</i>
03	reddish or tending to red stem	SPRUCE	<i>Picea abies (L.) H.Karst</i>
	Needle-like leaves similar to green/grey scales	CYPRESS	<i>Cupressus arizonica E.Greene</i>
04	Leaves composed of "leaflets"	05	
	Simple leaves (including deeply incised leaves)	06	
05	More than three leaflets	ROBINIA	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia L.</i>
06	Rather large smooth-margined leaves	WILDNUT	<i>Juglans regia L.</i>
	Expanded page leaves of various shapes toothed and/or lobed	07	
07	Leaf engraved by lobes	08	
	Whole leaf without lobed incisions	09	
08	Leaf divided into deep lobes whose margins have a few large, sharp teeth	OAK	<i>Quercus robur L.</i>
	Small leaves (< 10 cm), toothed margin and white lower page	WHITE POPLAR	<i>Populus alba L.</i>
09	Leaf with a triangular or rhombic shape	10	
	Heart-shaped leaves	11	
10	Leaf with lower page slightly different in color from upper page	BLACK POPLAR	<i>Populus nigra L.</i>
11	Leaves with asymmetrical base	LIME	<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>
	Leaves symmetrical base, rough on top, hairy underneath	BLACK MULBERRY	<i>Morus nigra L.</i>

APPENDIX 2 - Plant Traits

1 – Needle leaves

Leaves with a larger surface area

2 – Single needles

Clumps of 2 or 3 needles

3 – Needle-like, scale-like leaves

4 – Leaves composed of leaflets

Plain leaves

6 – Smooth-edged leaves

Leaves with toothed and/or lobed margins

9 – Triangular or rhombic leaf

Heart-shaped leaves

APPENDIX 3 – Turn photos into pictures with ImageJ

Sometimes it is necessary to change a photo into an image and/or drawing. There are several methods and software to perform this operation. In this paper we describe how to perform this operation with ImageJ software.

ImageJ is a digital image processing computer program, released in the public domain, based on Sun-Java; developed by the U.S. National Institutes of Health.

ImageJ was designed with an open architecture that provides for the possibility of having extensions via small "Java plugin" subprograms and many recordable macros.

ImageJ can be made to run as an online applet, as a downloadable application from the network, or on any computer (Mac, Linux, Windows) that has the Java 1.4 virtual machine or later versions installed¹.

Method

1. Open the photo you want to edit with ImageJ.

2. Select “Image” → “Adjust” → “Color Threshold” (in case of problems, you can convert the photo to 8-bit format and use the Threshold function).

3. Change the “Hue”, “Saturation” and “Brightness” parameters to match the selection to the subject in the photo to be transformed.

4. Select in the sequence “Select” → “Original” → “Select”.

5. Select with the dx key "Color Picker" → select the appropriate color.

6. Select → “Flood Fill Tool”.

7. Select the figure to be colored.

8. Save the figure in Tiff format or other format.

References

1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ImageJ>
2. <https://imagej.net/ij/docs/guide/user-guide.pdf>

APPENDIX 4 – Draw border with Gimp

If you need to draw a border around a figure you can use the GIMP software.

GNU Image Manipulation Program, commonly known by its acronym GIMP (/gimp/ GHIMP), is a free and open-source raster graphics editor used for image manipulation (retouching) and image editing, free-form drawing, transcoding between different image file formats, and more specialized tasks. It is extensible by means of plugins, and scriptable.

GIMP is released under the GPL-3.0-or-later license and is available for Linux, macOS, and Microsoft Windows¹.

Method

1. Open the figure you want to edit with GIMP.

2. Select by “Color Tool”

3. Select image

4. Select “Select” → “Border” → Border selection by es. 10 px (or another value)

5. Exchange foreground and background colors X → Color Black (or another desired color)

6. Select → “Bucket Fill Tool”

7. Zoom image

8. Select inside border

9. Deselect image
10. Exchange foreground and background colors X → Color White
11. Select → “Bucket Fill Tool”
12. Select inside image

12. Save the figure in Tiff format or other format.

References

1. <https://www.gimp.org/>
2. <https://www.gimp.org/docs/>